

Softmind

center for cognitive behavioral science and applied hypnosis

SOFTMIND & LAKSHMI HOSPITAL

SOFTMIND & LAKSHMI HOSPITAL
Kerala
Aroor, Alappuzha
Pin: 688 534

04/11/2021

Ref.No:156844/11/21

To Whom It May Concern

This is to certify that Mr **Jobin Albert** has undergone internship training at Softmind, Department of Psychology, Lakshmi Hospital, Aroor for a period of 1 (one) month with proper satisfaction.

During this period, we found he is sincere, honest, and a dedicated intern with a professional attitude and very good knowledge about the job.

His responsibilities were:

- 1) Plan psychological treatment programs that meet standard accreditation.
- 2) Review reports, case management review and visit psychiatric centres or hospitals to oversee procedure manual to assess need for further psychological services.
- 3) Develop, direct and participate in training programs.
- 4) Interview clients who presented with difficult and complex diagnostic problems and to assess their psychological status.
- 5) Review management of cases, assignments, case problems, issues and methods of treatment in collaboration with psychiatrist and other health care professionals to help develop comprehensive programs of therapy, evaluation and treatment.

Sincerely

PRASAD MK.Msc,(Psy)Mphil.(Psy) HPD
Licensed Clinical Rehabilitation Psychologist
RCI.:A50537
Softmind, Department of Psychotherapy, Lakshmi Hospital

PRASAD M.K, Msc (Psy) PGDRP, HPD (UK)
Licensed Reliab. Psychologist
Reg. No. RCI A50537.

METRO MIND

Dr. Thalhath P MBBS, MD (Consultant Psychiatrist)

Reg. No. 42842

CENTRE FOR NEUROPSYCHIATRY

Metromind: Rajagiri Road, Rajagiri P.O., Kalamassery, Cochin, Pin: 683104

Ph: 8281 152 680, 7306 808 8673 info@metromindhospital.com

www.metromindhospital.com

31/05/2022

Reg.no: D/62/2021/SMHA

Certificate

This is to certify that **Ms. AISHWARYA S, percuing MSW at SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, MANGALORE** has successfully completed 1 month Internship from (MAY 2nd TO MAY 31st 2022) at the Department of clinical psychology, Metro Mind Hospital, Kalamassery

During this period, we found she is sincere, honest and dedicated in understanding the cases and intervening patients effectively.

Her responsibilities were to:

- 1) Plan psychiatric treatment programs that meet standards of accreditation.
- 2) Review reports, case management and adhere to the hospital procedural manual to assess the need for psychiatric services.
- 3) Participate and Conduct training programs.
- 4) Interview clients who present difficult and complex diagnostic problems and to assess their psychological status.

We wish her all the best in future.

Sincerely,

Dr. Thalhath P. MBBS, MD
Consultant Psychiatrist
METRO MIND: Reg. No: 42842
CENTRE FOR NEUROPSYCHIATRY

Dr Thalhath P

MBBS, MD

CMD & Chief Psychiatrist

Dr Sunidharan

M.Phil., DCP, PhD

clinical psychologist

MARYMATHA HOSPITAL

& REVIVE MIND HEALTH

VAZHITHALA P.O., THODUPUZHA

IDUKKI (Dt.), KERALA - 685 583

PH : 04862 273162

04.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. NEETHUMOLB**, percuing **MSW** at **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY MANGALORE** has successfully completed 1 month Internship from (May 9th to June 4th 2022) at Mary Matha Hospital & Revive Mind Health, Thodupuzha.

During this period, we found she is sincere, honest and dedicated in understanding the cases and intervening patients effectively.

Her responsibility were to :

1. Plan Psychiatric treatment programs that meet standards of accreditation.
2. Review reports, case management and adhere to the Hospital procedural manual to assess the need for Psychiatric services.
3. Participate and conduct training programs .
4. Interview clients who present difficult and complex diagnostic problems and to assess their psychological status.

We wish her all the best in future.

Sincerely,

Dr. T. S. Thomas
MBBS, FCGP
Managing Director

Dr. Lakshmi G.I
MBBS, DPM
Consultant Psychiatrist

Dr. APARNA K. KAMAL
MBBS, DPM
Reg. No: 50165
Dr. Aparna K Kamal
MBBS, DPM
Consultant Psychiatrist

Dr. T.S. THOMAS
MBBS, FCGP
Reg. No: 14801

Dr. LEKSHMI. G.I
CONSULTANT PSYCHIATRIST
MBBS, DPM
TCMC Reg. No: 53690

NITTE
(Deemed to be University)

**JUSTICE K.S. HEGDE
CHARITABLE HOSPITAL**

CERTIFICATE

05-07-2022

This is to certify that **Mrs. Poornima Ganiga** IInd year MSW, from Srinivas University, has successfully completed her Internship work Practicum in the Department of Psychiatry as a part of M.S.W. course work from 10-05-2022 to 31-05-2022. During this period, she has been exposed to various therapeutic activities in De-Addiction and Psychiatry outpatients department.

Agneita
5/9/22
Mrs. Agneita Aiman
Lecturer in PSW
Department of Psychiatry
KSHEMA

Shrinivasa Bhat U
Dr. Shrinivasa Bhat U.
Prof & HOD
Department of Psychiatry
KSHEMA

Dr. Shrinivasa Bhat U.
Prof & HOD
Department of Psychiatry
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Ojin Foods Pvt Ltd, 2nd Floor,
Ummer Palace Building, Kuriyal Lane
Cherooty Road, Calicut, Kerala-673032

Date : 31-05-2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Miss. Veda Chandra** student of **Srinivas college Mangalore** has successfully completed internship at **Ojin Foods Pvt Ltd** , Kozhikode from **03 may 2022 to 31 may 2022**.

During her training period she has shown keen interest to learn and excel in her field. She was committed in her duties and tasks there by fulfilling most of the job function. Throughout her studies it is noteworthy that she is brilliant and her grasping power and hard work are second to none. She has brilliant future ahead and we wish her all success.

For OJIN FOODS PVT. LTD.

Managing Director)

INDIAN DESIGNS Exports Pvt. Ltd. Unit V

Manufacturers & Exporters of Readymade Garments

Ref No.: IDEPL/HRD/395/2022

Date: 30.05.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Yakshitha Shetty bearing Registration No. 7SU20SW815 a student of 4th Semester, MSW, Srinivas University, Mangalore. She has successfully completed her Internship Training in our organization from 06.05.2022 to 30.05.2022.

During her training she was found to be sincere and hard working.

We wish her all success in the future.

For Indian Designs Exports Pvt Ltd – Unit V

G. S. Karthik

DGM- HR&SC

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